

Handling Missing Values: A STACK-Based Assessment

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Handling missing data is an important but often neglected skill in statistics education. This paper presents a STACK-based formative assessment designed to address this gap by helping students develop strategies for interpreting and managing missing values. Using a simulated farm survey dataset, students must determine the most and least profitable crops and calculate average profits, while accounting for different types of missingness, such as whether a crop was not grown or grown but unsold. The assessment dynamically generates new datasets and uses STACK's Potential Response Trees (PRTs) to diagnose student misconceptions and deliver tailored feedback. Initial responses show common errors, such as treating all missing values the same or excluding them entirely. By surfacing these issues and encouraging reflection through immediate, specific, and iterative feedback, the assessment promotes deeper conceptual understanding. The approach is scalable, adaptable, and aligns with GAISE recommendations to use real data and focus on statistical reasoning in data science education.

INTRODUCTION

Missing data is a common challenge in real-world datasets and, if mishandled, can lead to biased or misleading conclusions (Dong & Peng, 2013). While various techniques exist for handling missingness (Little & Rubin, 2020), students often default to simplistic strategies such as deletion or mean substitution due to limited instruction on the topic (Peugh & Enders, 2004; Cox et al., 2014). This reflects a broader issue: despite its prevalence in real-world datasets, missing data is often overlooked in statistics education (Marron & Wahed, 2016). More recent reviews of educational research show that missing data methods are still underreported, and that traditional strategies like listwise deletion remain the default in many studies (Huang & Keller, 2025).

Missing values can arise from a range of causes, including non-response, data entry errors, and system limitations (Little & Rubin, 2020). The appropriate treatment of missing data depends on understanding these underlying causes (Rubin, 1976), yet many studies either fail to report their approach to missing data or apply naïve strategies such as listwise deletion or unconditional mean imputation (Peugh & Enders, 2004; Huang & Keller, 2025). As a result, poor data handling practices persist across both academic research and applied work.

This educational gap has been recognised by the Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE) College Report (Carver et al., 2016), which recommends exposing students to “typical issues such as missing observations.” However, there are few readily available tools for giving students realistic, feedback-rich practice with this topic. Consequently, students often graduate with limited ability to identify types of missingness or apply suitable strategies for addressing them in practice (Marron & Wahed, 2016).

This paper introduces a formative STACK assessment designed to address this gap. STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel) allows educators to create dynamic, auto-graded questions with feedback tailored to student responses (Sangwin, 2023). Using a simulated dataset on crop profitability, the assessment challenges students to reason through missing values and receive immediate, targeted feedback. We demonstrate how this tool can strengthen students' conceptual understanding of missing data and support deeper learning through repeated, reflective practice.

This work is also part of the ongoing efforts related to the African Data Initiative (ADI), which aims to promote accessible, relevant, and locally meaningful data education tools across the continent (Stern, 2017). By incorporating missing data handling into formative assessment in a contextually realistic scenario, this STACK-based approach contributes to the ADI goal of building stronger, locally grounded data skills.

BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE TO USING STACK

Students often approach missing data with oversimplified strategies, such as deleting incomplete rows or replacing all missing values with zero. These methods can compromise the validity of results particularly because, as Rubin (1976) emphasised, the cause of missingness should guide the response. For example, skipping an income question (Missing Not at Random) differs from a sensor failure (Missing Completely at Random), yet students frequently treat these cases alike.

Despite its importance, the topic of missing data remains underrepresented in teaching materials. Students often finish introductory or even intermediate statistics courses without learning to distinguish between different types of missingness, or understanding the consequences of handling them inappropriately (Peugh & Enders, 2004). This reflects a broader educational challenge: teaching students not just procedures, but also the reasoning behind data decisions.

STACK provides an opportunity to change this. Unlike standard quiz platforms, STACK uses Potential Response Trees (PRTs) to detect specific misconceptions, such as treating missing values as zeros, conflating MCAR with MAR, or defaulting to listwise deletion. STACK can then deliver targeted feedback based on the identified misconception. STACK can also randomise datasets for each attempt, supporting repeated practice and reducing the likelihood of memorised answers. This system encourages students to think critically and apply concepts to new situations – key components of statistical reasoning highlighted in the GAISE College Report (2016). These principles remain relevant and are being reinforced in the forthcoming update to the GAISE guidelines (Perrett, 2024), which continues to emphasise teaching statistics as an investigative process, grounded in real data and supported by thoughtful, formative assessment.

The STACK-based question developed for this study reflects these principles. Students are presented with a simulated dataset on farm crop profitability, with missing values that require interpretation based on their cause. The assessment is designed not just to test calculations, but to promote deeper engagement with the nature of missing data and the consequences of different handling strategies.

ASSESSMENT DESIGN

The assessment is built around a simulated farm survey dataset with incomplete records, reflecting the messiness of real-world data (Figure 1). Each farm reports on three staple crops (e.g., maize, sorghum, millet), including whether each was grown, sold (if grown), and the profit earned (if sold). Some profit values are missing, either because the crop was not grown or because it was grown but not sold (e.g., due to crop failure, or retained for home consumption). The distinction between these two causes is essential, as it influences how missingness should be handled in profit calculations.

The STACK question is structured to guide students through an analysis that requires careful consideration of these missing values. It comprises three main questions:

- Which of the three crops is the most profitable overall?
- Which of the three crops is the least profitable overall?
- What is the mean profit for a specific crop (e.g., Sorghum) across all farms where it was grown and sold?

To discourage rote memorisation, STACK generates a unique dataset for each attempt, randomising farm-level data while keeping the logic consistent. This allows students to practice the same conceptual task multiple times with fresh data.

Importantly, the STACK question is software-agnostic. Students are free to use whatever tools they prefer – spreadsheet software, calculators, or programming languages – to perform their analysis. This ensures that the emphasis remains on reasoning about the data and the nature of the missingness, rather than on learning a particular software tool. The goal is to build conceptual understanding that is transferable across analytical environments.

The design also ensures that students are confronted with the consequences of their choices. The dataset is constructed such that the answers to the first two questions depend directly on how the student has handled the missing values. If a student ignores all missing profits (e.g., excludes any farm with a missing profit when computing averages), the results will indicate that sorghum is the most profitable and millet the least. However, if the student correctly accounts for the reason behind each missing value, the conclusion is reversed: millet becomes the most profitable, and sorghum the least.

Let's consider a survey conducted with 100 farms to gather information about their crop habits. Each farm was asked three specific questions regarding Maize, Sorghum, and Millet. ⓘ Question is missing tests or variants.

1. Did they grow the crop last year?
2. If yes, did the crop succeed enough to be sold?
3. If sold, what was their profit?

Download Data

Use the data provided to determine:

1. (a) Which crop was the most profitable **on average**?
- (b) Which one was the least profitable **on average**?
2. What is the mean profit for Sorghum?

Figure 1. The STACK question given, with the option to download the randomised data.

This stark reversal offers a powerful teaching opportunity. It highlights that the way missing data are treated can completely alter the narrative, even in a seemingly straightforward analysis. The third question, which asks for the mean profit of a specific crop, serves as a diagnostic tool: it helps identify which assumptions or imputation strategy the student has applied. By triangulating the responses across these questions, the assessment can more precisely diagnose conceptual misunderstandings and tailor feedback accordingly.

“Correct” handling of missing values in this scenario involves differentiating between the two causes of missingness. For instance, when calculating the overall profitability of a certain crop:

- If a farm did not grow a crop, this farm should be excluded from the calculation of average profit for that crop, or its profit for that crop considered zero if the question implies average profit across all farms for that crop.
- If a farm grew a crop but did not sell it, this might be treated as zero profit for that farm’s crop enterprise, as no income was generated from sales.

This context-sensitivity is at the heart of the assessment. The aim is not to test arithmetic, but to challenge students to reason about what each missing value represents in real-world terms.

The logic used by STACK to detect student errors is embedded in its PRT. These PRTs analyse the student’s numerical answers and can be designed to identify common misconceptions, such as:

- Ignoring missing values: Students may calculate averages from non-missing values only, effectively performing listwise deletion. If missingness is non-random, this can introduce bias.
- Replacing all missing values with zero: This is a common simplistic strategy. The PRT can detect if the student’s calculations are consistent with replacing every missing profit value with 0, regardless of whether the crop was grown or not. This would incorrectly penalise crops that simply weren’t cultivated by some farms.
- Replacing missing values with the mean (of observed values): Another common but often inappropriate method. The PRT can detect if the student has applied this by comparing the submitted answer to expected results under mean imputation.
- Failing to differentiate between types of missingness: This is the core conceptual error the question is designed to target. The PRT can compare the student’s answers against expected values derived from correctly differentiating these two types of missingness. For example, if a student’s calculation for “most profitable crop” matches an outcome where all missing values were treated as zero, this indicates a failure to differentiate.

The design ensures that students engage with a realistic scenario in which correct interpretation, not just calculation, is essential. By surfacing misconceptions through analysis of the answers, the STACK system supports a more diagnostic and reflective learning process.

STUDENT RESPONSES AND FINDINGS

This STACK-based assessment has been used in foundational statistics and data skills courses aimed at undergraduate and postgraduate university students, as well as working professionals. The question is embedded within an introductory course that covers key data handling concepts such as filtering, reshaping, pivot tables, and data visualisation. The course is designed to be software-agnostic, with an emphasis on developing practical understanding of messy, real-world data.

The findings presented here are based on informal, initial observations rather than a formal study. Students were given unlimited time to complete the assessment, allowing them to engage with the feedback and reflect on their approach without pressure. While no controlled evaluation has been conducted yet, the STACK system enables instructors to observe trends in student responses and how those evolve over multiple attempts. These observations reveal several recurring patterns in student responses and demonstrate how personalised feedback can support learning.

Common Misconceptions

Two misconceptions have repeatedly occurred. First, many students relied on listwise deletion, basing their answers only on farms with complete profit data. This approach can reduce the data set and introduce bias if the missingness is not random. Second, students frequently replaced all missing profit values with zero. This failed to distinguish between farms that *did not grow* a crop and those that grew it but made *no sales*, leading to incorrect profitability rankings.

Although the STACK system does not formally track students' intentions (e.g., whether they explicitly chose mean imputation or listwise deletion), student input can often be interpreted based on the response to the crops which provides the best and worst profit, and to the student's calculated mean profit of a particular crop. For example, a mean calculated from only non-missing values suggests listwise deletion, while the inclusion of zeros for all missing values likely indicates a blanket replacement strategy. These patterns, when repeated across student responses, allow educators to infer common reasoning paths.

Impact of Feedback

The personalised feedback provided by STACK appeared to guide students toward more accurate and nuanced reasoning. When feedback flagged the distinction between "not grown" and "grown but not sold," many students adjusted their calculations accordingly in subsequent attempts. This shift suggested a move away from simplistic, one-size-fits-all strategies and toward a more contextually informed approach.

Anecdotally, students who initially averaged only non-missing values for a crop often revised their calculations after feedback. In later attempts, they might correctly exclude farms that didn't grow that crop, while including zero profits for those that grew but didn't sell it – demonstrating a clearer grasp of the meaning behind the missing data.

As more students engage with this question, we aim to continue refining the feedback provided. One of STACK's strengths is its adaptability: when multiple students give the same incorrect answer, it becomes possible to identify a new misconception and extend the system to catch and respond to it. In this way, the question is continually improved to address a broader range of student misunderstandings.

FEEDBACK AND ADAPTABILITY

STACK's ability to provide personalised and adaptive feedback is central to its pedagogical value in this assessment. STACK's PRTs evaluate not just whether an answer is correct, but what reasoning it likely reflects. This allows it to diagnose misconceptions and respond with targeted guidance.

For instance, if a student treats all missing profit values as zero, STACK might respond: "It appears you've treated all missing profit values as £0. Some profits may be missing because the crop wasn't grown, others because it wasn't sold. Should both be treated the same? Consider how this

affects your profitability comparison.” Or, if the mean profit for sorghum excludes farms that grew but didn’t sell it: “You’ve correctly identified the most profitable crop. But when calculating sorghum’s mean profit, are you including all farms that grew it – even those with zero sales?”

Such feedback encourages students to reflect on their assumptions, not just correct their arithmetic. The emphasis is on helping students understand why certain approaches to missing data are more appropriate than others in a given scenario. It supports learning by being:

- Immediate: Students receive feedback instantly, allowing them to reflect while the problem is fresh in their mind.
- Specific: Feedback is tied to the specific errors detected in their response.
- Iterative: Each attempt generates a new dataset, encouraging deeper engagement through repeated practice. This encourages mastery through practice

Formative assessment and feedback, like that provided by STACK, can address common misconceptions by encouraging deeper reasoning. Rather than checking only for correct final answers, well-designed assessments reveal misunderstandings and guide students through reflection and revision, sometimes simultaneously exemplifying the adverse effects of their mishandling of data. Feedback that targets conceptual understanding – especially when personalised – supports the development of sound analytical habits. This aligns with constructivist approaches to learning, which emphasise active engagement, meaningful feedback, and learning through experience (Black & Wiliam, 2009).

DISCUSSION

Based on the literature and the conducted analyses, this STACK-based assessment can provide a strong foundation to handle missing data in real-world contexts. By combining a realistic dataset, context-dependent missingness, and feedback targeted at common misconceptions, the assessment encourages students to move beyond simple strategies and think critically about why data are missing and how that should influence their analysis. The dynamic generation of datasets ensures that students must understand the underlying principles rather than memorising solutions to specific instances.

The initial responses often confirm that students may enter statistics courses with an underdeveloped understanding of how to handle missing data, often defaulting to overly simple or inappropriate methods. The assessment helps reveal these misconceptions, such as treating all missing values identically or ignoring the context of missingness. The iterative process, supported by STACK’s feedback, provides a pathway to rectify these misunderstandings.

STACK offers several distinct advantages for this type of assessment:

- Contextualised Problem Solving: STACK allows for the creation of problems grounded in realistic scenarios where the meaning of data (and missing data) is paramount.
- Detection of Specific Errors: The Potential Response Tree logic enables the pre-identification of common student errors and the delivery of tailored feedback for each.
- Personalised Feedback: Feedback can be designed to address the student’s specific incorrect reasoning, guiding them towards a more correct conceptual understanding.
- Randomisation for Mastery: The ability to generate unique datasets for each attempt supports learning through repeated practice and encourages genuine understanding.
- Focus on Conceptual Understanding: The system can be programmed to reward correct reasoning and penalise common conceptual errors, shifting the focus from mere calculation to understanding.

Designing such assessments is not without challenges. Creating robust PRTs that anticipate a wide range of student reasoning requires careful planning. Some nuanced misunderstandings may go undetected if they do not match predefined patterns. Finally, while STACK excels at assessing numerical logic, it is less effective at capturing qualitative reasoning unless supported by additional free-text prompts, which are harder to auto-mark.

However, the underlying logic is highly adaptable. The structure used here, distinguishing between types of missingness and using that distinction to guide analysis, can easily be applied to other datasets or domains. Whether dealing with sales records, patient data, or survey responses, the underlying STACK question structure and PRT logic for differentiating types of missingness would remain largely the same, requiring mainly changes to variable names and contextual narratives.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

This paper presented a STACK-based assessment designed to address an important but often under-taught topic in statistics education: handling missing data. By using dynamic datasets, targeted feedback through PRTs, and realistic scenarios, the assessment encourages students to move beyond simplistic methods and develop context-sensitive reasoning.

The educational impact lies in better preparing students to confront the messy realities of real-world data, in helping students recognise that different types of missingness require different treatments, and that these choices can significantly alter conclusions. Initial findings suggest that this method helps identify common misconceptions and, through iterative practice and targeted feedback, guides students towards more appropriate and thoughtful data handling techniques.

Future work will focus on enhancing PRT logic to capture a broader range of student strategies, and conducting formal studies to assess the assessment's impact on student learning outcomes. In addition, future work plans to scale this assessment more widely available across different cohorts and contexts. By integrating feedback-rich, realistic tasks like this into statistics instruction, we can help students build stronger analytical habits and prepare them for the complexities of working with real-world data.

Additionally, the assessment's software-agnostic nature ensures that students can focus on reasoning and data understanding, rather than the mechanics of a particular tool. This aligns with the broader vision of the African Data Initiative (ADI), which advocates for flexible, locally relevant, and accessible data education methods (Stern, 2017). By designing assessments that are conceptually rich, adaptable to diverse settings, and independent of specific platforms, this approach supports inclusive and scalable data literacy education, especially in resource-constrained or varied digital environments.

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